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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE INTERNET OF THINGS AS INNOVATIVE METHODS FOR IMPROVING THE AGRO-INDUSTRIAL SECTOR

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Abstract: The article analyzes the prospects for the use of artificial intelligence technologies in agriculture in the Sverdlovsk region. The relevance of the study is due to the rapid development of these technologies based on various breakthroughs in the digital sphere and the significant uncertainty in the prospects for their application in agricultural production. At the preparatory stage, an analysis of publications in the WoS network was carried out, which makes it possible to specify the essence and scope of artificial intelligence technologies in agriculture.

Keywords: agriculture, artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence strategy, artificial intelligence technologies, big data, digital agriculture, digital economy, internet of things, machine learning, robotics, survey

Introduction

The agro-industrial sector, both in Uzbekistan and in other economically and technologically developed countries, needs to constantly search for and implement the most effective methods of applying information technologies. First of all, this is due to the conditions of the modern market, the speed of the implementation of operational and production activities and the intensification of

competition in the agro-industrial complex. Agriculture remains one of the most important sectors of the economy of a large number of developed countries. However, aspects such as climate change and population growth are major challenges in industries capable of producing enough crops for everyone. This has led business leaders to look for new innovative approaches to improve the yield of their crops. One of the most important solutions currently being implemented is AI or artificial intelligence.

The purpose of the study, therefore, is to study and analyze the functionality of the most innovative and trending technologies in the agricultural sector, as well as the possibilities of the Internet of things in agriculture. Materials, methods and objects of research - the regional and federal levels of the agro-industrial complex of the Russian Federation. AI-related technologies used in agriculture fall into five categories:

- 1) agricultural robots;
 - 2) crop and soil monitoring;
 - 3) predictive analysis;
 - 4) neural sensors;
 - 5) tracking animals. Each of these unique advances has its own benefits. Understanding and embracing these benefits could be the next big step in agriculture. Looking deeper into each category, it's incredible to see what the new technology is capable of [1].
- Agricultural robotics: weeds. The use of robotics is found in almost every industry these days, and agriculture is no exception. The application of artificial intelligence in agriculture is aimed at helping farmers gain control over weeds that threaten crop destruction and damage. This is becoming more of an issue as weeds become resistant to pesticides. The benefit of automation allows farmers to spend less time getting rid of these weeds and more time harvesting. Modern robots use special "computer vision" to control the growth of weeds and spray them on modern pesticides. The precision achieved by these robots helps to reduce chemical waste by up to 20% by using a concentrated

spray to irrigate weeds. Working independently through a complex AI system, they bring really great benefits to business entities.

Agricultural robotics: harvesting. Automated robots can do more than just clear weeds, which means more advanced functionality and use as a workforce. At harvest time, a shortage of labor can result in the loss of a huge amount of potential income. This is where assembly robots come in. Strawberry farmers in Florida, USA, for example, are already using these robots to harvest their crops during the peak season. Not only does this allow them to sell more of their crops, but it significantly reduces labor costs, which are approximately 40% of annual farming costs. Harvesting robots work collaboratively, one of them moving around the field, in which there are others who choose the crop, and instinctively know where to go according to AI technology. They don't look like a robot vacuum in moving around a designated area, but their ability to communicate with each other and work effectively with each other is a technological marvel. Crop production and soil: health. Deforestation to free land for agricultural land and moderate degradation of soil quality significantly affect both the quality of crops produced and their sale, having a negative impact on the economy as a whole. Until now, it has not been possible to successfully deal with this natural phenomenon. With the help of artificial intelligence technologies, in particular electronic applications for deep learning, farmers are able to find potential nutrient deficiencies in the soil. The system uses algorithms coupled with image recognition that tracks changes in plants present when there are defects in the soil, crop-destroying pests, or plant diseases spreading across the field. Farmers only need to take a picture with their smartphone and then upload the image to the app. After assessing the problem, farmers are provided with soil restoration techniques and other solutions that will help improve the quality and quantity of the crop. To date, these AI systems have an estimated accuracy of 95%. However, concrete research results are not yet available. Further study of the application of these technologies is still required in order to fully understand the effectiveness and

usefulness for application, including in the future. Cultivated plants and soil: an analysis. The agricultural industry can use drones, and AI provides ample opportunities in crop analysis. Farmers can now pre-program the desired flight path for the drone so that it can scan crops using "computer vision" technology. Images can be saved for later analysis via USB. The information is uploaded to a cloud platform where algorithms are used to analyze the crop data found in the images. The software used in the cloud recognizes any form of bacteria and other crop health problems that farmers may face. The technology, with the ability to scan an average of 20 hectares in less than 30 minutes, gives farmers important insights into future yields, as well as what steps need to be taken to improve the health of their crops. Intelligent analysis: satellites. Satellite imaging has dozens of applications, and the agricultural industry is now using the technology to better predict weather and analyze crop tolerances.

AI-assisted machine learning algorithms are already being used in the daily analysis of weather forecasts for news stations, and these same systems could be an accurate enough source of data to inform farmers of upcoming problems early on. Farms can now predict: –temperatures; -precipitation; -wind speed; - solar radiation; - cyclones; –drought. At the same time, satellite imaging is being used to analyze the health status of crops and track the spread of various diseases that affect plants. Farmers using this technology can pinpoint exactly where fertilizer might be needed or which parts of their farms are prone to pest attacks right from their smartphone screens. Satellite imaging will enable the agricultural industry to save significant amounts of money every year that could otherwise be wasted on the use of pesticides and fertilizers. While this technology is still completely innovative and practically unrealized, it has incredible potential for agriculture and the country's economy. Neural sensors: insect control. Neural sensor farming is something to look at in the coming years, as technology can radically change the impact of pests and diseases of crops in the agro-industrial complex. A neural implant is placed in the brain of an insect to monitor or even

influence behavioral patterns. These neural sensors are currently being used for medical and animal studies. But recently, the study of the behavior of insects is relevant, which will provide a promising opportunity to control their behavior in favor of humans. This can be done in one of two ways. The first one involves the introduction of these sensors on known pests in order to deter their behavior, taking them as far as possible from areas where they can spoil crops. Since the neural sensors are controlled by radio frequency, it is possible to correct the direction of a certain number of pests with the push of a button, which may well rid the crop field of insects heading towards it. The second option is to use these sensors for those species of the animal world that destroy pests. This would allow farmers to prevent harmful influences by correcting the behavior of inhabitants that are safe for farming. It is important to note that both of these solutions are still theoretical. The military is currently testing the use of neural sensors on various insects and sharks to survey potentially hazardous areas, showing potential for a wide range of applications. For example, this concept was used in the computer game WARFRAME, where players can control swarms of insects.

Animal Tracking: "Smart Cows". Another innovation using artificial intelligence in agriculture uses face recognition technology; the same is used in the Snapchat app to create custom filters. Until now, farmers have relied on physical tracking devices to keep track of livestock. Face recognition allows you to completely eliminate this process. With one device, farmers can not only monitor their livestock, but also: –monitor the behavior of the herd; - monitor the feeding habits of animals; –Detect and treat animal diseases at an early stage. In addition to saving on the cost of physical trackers, facial recognition devices have the potential to be more valuable to farmers with the benefits listed above. Animal husbandry becomes healthier, at the same time the risk of chaotic and uncontrolled movement of the herd is minimized.

The processes of digitalization of agriculture and the economy of Uzbekistan as a whole will involve in the development of joint IoT solutions all players in the

value chain of the agricultural sector in one or another combination in interaction with each other. A universal rule in IoT technologies and accompanying big data aggregation processes is that the more data is collected in one place, the smarter the system becomes and the more valuable information can be obtained for consumers. Provided that the most modern models of their processing are used. IoT and digitalization (automation) in agriculture is also an opportunity to create complex highly automated production and logistics chains covering wholesale and retail trade companies, logistics, agricultural producers and their suppliers in a single process with adaptive management. Such chains can significantly reduce the cost and retail prices of food products, thus increasing their availability for consumers and, as a result, production and sales volumes (Fig.). The segments adjacent to production take up to 75% of the profits, and according to the EU, the marginality of the farming business in 2011 was no more than 21%, with a downward trend. In the relationship between agricultural producers and participants in the supply chain (wholesale companies, logistics, retail chains), it is promising to switch to a direct sales model, in which the manufacturer “sees” the end consumer, his volume and demand structure, and through the use of predictive analytics models produces exactly what and when the consumer needs, and product supply management is carried out on the principles of automatic exchange of information between participants in the supply chain and minimal use of the warehouse and logistics infrastructure of wholesale intermediaries.

The implementation of such a model of relationships in the value chain of agricultural products, based on the technologies of the Internet of things and end-to-end automation of production and business processes, will allow: dropshipping and, as a result, a reduction in the markup in the wholesale and retail sector, as well as due to a 3-5-fold increase in labor productivity in agriculture, which will increase consumption in monetary terms by at least three times; thus, the volume of the market for food and agricultural products can grow by 1.5 times - by 4 trillion. rubles in annual terms, and the increase in the net profit of agricultural

producers can reach up to 200 billion rubles. in annual terms.–Dramatically increase the level of automation of the main production and business processes of agricultural enterprises, including small ones, which will increase the consumption of information technologies by agricultural enterprises by 156 billion rubles. (+22% to the existing volume of the IT market in Uzbekistan) and data transmission services for 11 billion rubles. per year (+19% to the current consumption of data transmission services for corporate sectors in Uzbekistan). – The transition to end-to-end highly automated production and supply chains of agricultural products will make this process transparent for banks and allow them to minimize the risks of lending to agricultural producers. This will create prerequisites for increasing the volume of lending to agricultural producers by 500 billion sums. Solving the problem of increasing labor productivity in agriculture by 3-5 times, which is not solved within the framework of traditional models of relationships between the supplier of mechanization and automation, but solved within the framework of models based on IoT, will require:

–Create skilled jobs in rural areas with a high level of pay and a high multiplier (one highly skilled job creates another 10-15 new jobs).

–Nine times (by 85 billion rubles in annual terms) to increase the consumption of mineral fertilizers.

–Dramatically increase the level of mechanization of basic operations in agriculture, which will form the market for "digital rental" of mechanization equipment (tractors, combines) and create additional demand for agricultural tractors in Uzbekistan in the amount of 600 thousand units. (60 annual production volumes in Uzbekistan) and 200 thousand combines. Thus, the total economic effect from the transition of agriculture to business models based on IoT and digitalization can be more than 4.8 trillion. rub. in annual terms, or 5.6% of the GDP growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan (relative to the indicators for 2016), and a possible increase in the volume of information technology consumption in Uzbekistan could be + 22%, moreover, due to the digitalization of only one

industry - agriculture. Large vertically integrated agricultural holdings create maximum added value and will be the main "industrial environment" for the implementation of IoT innovations in agriculture. In the near future, large businesses and advanced medium-sized enterprises will become the main consumer of AIoT technologies in Uzbekistan due to the ability to attract investments and readiness for technological innovations. Large agro-industrial complex can be pioneers in the implementation of IoT-based automated farm management systems, autonomous agrobots, mastering the methods of innovative mathematics necessary for processing big agricultural data.

And also to take an active position in the organization of training, advanced training, conducting trainings and introducing a mentoring system, organizing business trips to get acquainted with leading foreign companies and their achievements, daily practices. Another promising segment for the use of AIoT solutions, and possibly the leader in terms of the effect of their implementation in the domestic agricultural sector, can be medium-sized private agricultural enterprises. They have sufficient flexibility in the choice, testing and active use of new technologies in the production process, are motivated for results and have sufficient financial resources to invest in IT infrastructure. In Uzbekistan, there is a significant backlog to increase domestic production of basic products, develop new types of industries with export potential, increase mechanization, automation, productivity of agriculture and related industries. The task of the export market is to develop projects that increase the localization of the entire chain of economic redistribution on the territory of Uzbekistan, which will increase the gross value added of agriculture and the transition to the export of processed products rather than raw materials. A possible barrier is outdated equipment, lack of technology, lack of investment. To maximize the potential of Internet of Things projects in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to solve a whole range of tasks related to the development of the IoT ecosystem; adoption and dissemination of the cloud technology model; conviction in the economic feasibility of combining and

exchanging data on the performance of their activities; improving education and qualifications not only in the field of innovative agriculture, but also in such areas as "IT in agriculture", "mathematics, big data analysis, AI in agriculture", "robotics in agriculture", "automation and control business processes." Of strategic importance for the industry are: the development of domestic agricultural science, the restoration and development of its own seed fund, plant genetics and biotechnology, the development of the domestic sector of agrochemistry, the growth of agricultural mechanization (harvesters, tractors, drones, robotics, small self-propelled and other agricultural machinery).

Conclusion

The results of the study made it possible to draw a number of conclusions that the integrated implementation of the technologies under consideration and activities related to them, as well as the elimination of constraining factors and the introduction of digital automation and the Internet of Things projects will contribute to: –reducing the lag in agricultural productivity from the level of developed countries; –increasing the attractiveness of the industry for investors, entrepreneurs, employees; –improving living conditions in rural areas; –raising the level of qualification, competitiveness, wages of employees; –development of the domestic ecosystem of developers with export potential; –development within Uzbekistan of new highly competitive specialties: Big Data, Data Science, Machine learning, Artificial Intelligence; –increase in demand for domestic engineering products; –increase in demand for R&D and domestic innovations; –development of agricultural and biotechnological science; –development of new types of insurance services; –development of new e-commerce platforms in agriculture (both for the sale of food products and raw materials for agricultural production); - the emergence of a large number of analytical companies, companies developing innovative services for agriculture [6]. Addressing issues such as the coming global food shortage will require the concerted efforts of

countries, organizations and communities around the world. The initialization of the considered innovative methods in order to increase yields, reduce losses and increase the efficiency of the agricultural production process will be of great importance for improving the level of food security of both the region in particular and the country as a whole. Thus, by combining the efforts of the state, science and business, the result will be the opportunity to create one of the most innovative industries not only in Uzbekistan, but throughout the world.

REFERENCES

1. Moskalev S.M. Internet-tehnologii i reklama v biznese: uchebnoye posobiye. – SPb: SPbGAU, 2018. – 99 s.
2. FarmBeats: AI & IoT for Agriculture Established: May 14, 2015 [Elektronnyy resurs]. – URL: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/farmbeats-iot-agriculture> (data obrashcheniya: 15.06.2018).
3. Guerra M. 3 Ways the IoT Revolutionizes Farming, 2017 // Electronic Design [Elektronnyy resurs]. – URL: <http://www.electronicdesign.com/analog/3-ways-iot-revolutionizes-farming> (data obrashcheniya: 22.06.2018).